

ISic1497

Epitaph for Caius Terentius Symphorus

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Found in 1914 in exavations by Orsi in the , sep.104

Coordinates

38.1992517, 15.5566385

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3573

Physical Description

A marble slab, with lightly convex surface, broken into three joining pieces (and restored). The upper left corner is missing. Part of a damaged moulding projects along the upper edge.

Dimensions

Height 26.2 cm

Width 29.8 cm

Depth 1-1.7 cm

Layout

The text is carefully aligned on the left margin, less evenly along the right, and fills the stone over 5 lines, with a large hederā at the end of the text, lower right.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-5: 33-34 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation lines 1 to 5: 11-15 mm

Text

1. [C(aio)·] Terentio · Symphoro
2. C(ai) · Terenti · Syntrophî · lib(erto)
3. medico chir(urgo) · coh(ortis) · IIII
4. praet(oriae) · ann(orū) · XXIIX · huius
5. cura(m) · egit · Atticus

Apparatus

Text after Bitto 2001

Translation (en)

To Caius Terentius Symphorus, freedman of Caius Terentius Syntrophus, surgeon of the 4th Praetorian Cohort, died aged 28 (or 'surgeon for 28 years').

Atticus took care of this.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175832

EDR 073509

EDCS 14805798

PHI 313639

Bibliography

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